

ENGLISH READING SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS AND READING COMPREHENSION OF GRADE VI PUPILS

DIANE CATHYRIE N. DE GUZMAN¹

CECILIA Q. VELASCO²

dianecathyrine.deguzman@deped.gov.ph¹

cqvelasco@yahoo.com²

0000-0002-9745-7597¹

0000-0027-900-6469²

Sta. Catalina Norte School, Candelaria, Quezon, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

New normal brought drastic changes and challenges in education. Many institutions opted to use modular distance learning as their mode of learning delivery. This phenomena was new to everyone, both teachers and learners struggled on how to continue provide quality education in this pandemic time. As there were some instances that text book and self-learning module did not suffice learning of the students. Supplementary learning materials necessitate in improving learners' skill particularly their reading comprehension. This study focused in investigating the effect of using English reading supplementary materials in reading comprehension of Grade 6 students at Sta. Catalina Norte Elementary School. Grade 6 pupils in Sta. Catalina Norte Elementary School, in Sta. Catalina Norte, Candelaria East District, were chosen as the respondents of the study. The one-group pretest and post-test reading comprehension test consisting context clue, main idea and inferencing, activity sheets with blogs and news articles as reading supplementary materials, was used as the main data-gathering instrument. The result of the variables showed a significant difference between the pre and post test scores of the students in reading comprehension after using English reading supplementary materials and modular instruction. This indicates that the use of activity sheets in reading comprehension has improved significantly from instructional to independent level of reading. This also suggests that the activity sheets used by the researcher were effective supplementary materials for reading of the students. Despite of this result, as for the recommendations, teachers must craft activity sheet as supplementary materials in improving the comprehension skills of the pupils by increasing the time of teaching reading comprehension lessons and not only part of the discussion, separate time may be considered focusing on reading comprehension alone and can be a research reference to those students who wants to have a farther study along this line. In the same manner, the results of this study could be a great reference in the conduct of an action research.

Keywords: English reading supplementary materials, reading comprehension, blogs, news article, context clue, main idea, inferencing